

GEOBIONTS WERE FOUND IN COTTON FIELDS IRRIGATED BY THE DRIP METHOD.

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Annotation: This study examines the species composition and quantitative indicators of geophilous insects in cotton fields using drip irrigation. It was found that this irrigation method significantly influences the structure of soil biota, creating favorable conditions for certain species. Dominant and rare species were identified, as well as their ecological significance in the agrocenosis. The obtained results are important for assessing the biological state of the soil and developing integrated plant protection methods.

Keywords: geophilous insects, drip irrigation, cotton, soil fauna, agroecosystem, biodiversity, ecological factors, population structure, pests, beneficial species, integrated pest management

The study of soil geophiles in agroecosystems where cotton is grown using simple drip irrigation is one of the most pressing scientific areas today. The simple drip irrigation method plays a significant role in conserving water resources, significantly increasing productivity, and reducing soil degradation. At the same time, this technology has a positive effect on the physicochemical and biological properties of the soil. In particular, noticeable changes have been observed in the composition of soil insects—geophiles—and their ecological grouping. Geophiles are an integral part of the soil ecosystem, ensuring the decomposition of organic matter, the formation of humus, improving soil structure, and the stability of food chains [1].

Drip irrigation results in an uneven distribution of soil moisture, creating wet and dry zones. This leads to a spatial redistribution of the geophile population. While some species prefer moisture and can thrive in drip-irrigated areas, such conditions are likely to be unfavorable for others [2]. Furthermore, drip irrigation also alters the soil temperature regime. This factor directly impacts the development cycle, reproduction rate, and period of insect activity. As a result, the balance between beneficial and harmful insects in an agroecosystem can shift. For example, while an increase in the number of predatory geophiles contributes to the natural reduction of pests, an increase in the number of some phytophages can harm the crop [3].

Another important aspect of studying geophiles in cotton agroecosystems is the development of integrated protection systems. In modern agriculture, there is a growing need to reduce the use of chemicals and widely implement biological

methods. In this regard, the possibilities for natural management of agroecosystems are expanding through an in-depth study of the composition and dynamics of soil fauna.

The study of geophiles in cotton fields with drip irrigation has not only theoretical but also practical significance. This research will help improve soil fertility, ensure environmental sustainability, and efficiently use resources in agriculture.

Research methods. Firstly, the most common method for counting soil and above-ground insects was the use of Barber traps. This method was initially widely used by Western European soil entomologists, particularly methods developed on the basis of the classic work of H.E. Barber (1931) [1]. For counting dung beetles (Scarabaeidae) and ants, the quadrat and transect methods were used. This approach was based on the principles of "Ecological Methods" by Southwood and Henderson (2000) [2]. The catalogues "Fauna of Europe" and "Coleoptera of the Palearctic" for such species as Aphodius fimetarius, Onthophagus hecate, Copris lunaris, Copris hispanus, Balthasar (1963-1964) - Scarabaeidae USSR, Lasius niger, Messor kisilkumensis, Tetramorium caespitum, Seifert (2007) - Ants of Central and Northern Europe were used. [4,5,6,7].

Research results and analysis. Table 1 presents the species composition and quantitative indicators of geophilous insects detected in cotton agrocenoses under drip irrigation. These data are of significant scientific importance for assessing the structure of the soil biocenoses, ecological stability, and trophic relationships in the agroecosystem.

According to the analysis of Table 1, some species demonstrated high activity under drip irrigation. In particular, the highest indicators were recorded for Scarites subcylindricus, Scarites terricola, and Agriotes meticulosus. This indicates that these species are adapted to localized increases in soil moisture. These insects are often predatory or semi-predatory and play an important role in the natural regulation of pest populations in the agrocenoses.

Table 1.

Number of geobiont insects found in drip-irrigated cotton fields.

Nº	Typs	Tomch Geobionts in cotton fields (grain crops) irrigated by drip method.
1	<i>Broscus punctatus</i>	8
2	<i>Scarites subcylindricus</i>	9

3	<i>Scarites terricola</i>	9
4	<i>Scarites angustus</i>	-
5	<i>Siagona europaea</i>	4
6	<i>Agrotis segetum</i>	5
7	<i>Aphodius fimetarius</i>	3
8	<i>Onthophagus hecate</i>	2
9	<i>Lasius niger</i>	8
10	<i>Messor kisilkumensis Arnoldi</i>	-
11	<i>Tetramorium caespitum</i>	6
12	<i>Copris lunaris</i>	-
13	<i>Copris hispahus</i>	-
14	<i>Blaps halophile</i>	-
15	<i>Zabrus morio</i>	8
16	<i>Agriotes meticulosus</i>	9

The ants *Brosicus punctatus*, *Lasius niger*, and *Zabrus morio* also have relatively high values (8). These species are ecologically widely adaptable and can thrive in a variety of moisture conditions. In particular, *Lasius niger* ants actively contribute to improving soil structure, increasing aeration, and decomposing organic matter. Therefore, their presence is considered a positive indicator of the agroecosystem.

Moderate values are observed for the species *Tetramorium caespitum* (6), *Agrotis segetum* (5), *Siagona europaea* (4), and *Aphodius fimetarius* (3). These species belong to different trophic groups in the agrocenosis and contribute to food web stability. For example, *Agrotis segetum* is a phytophage, and its presence indicates the need for improved agricultural practices. In contrast, saprophagous ants such as *Aphodius fimetarius* decompose organic matter and contribute to soil fertility. Low or zero values were noted for *Scarites angustus* and *Messor kisilkumensis Arnoldi*. This indicates the sensitivity of these species to drip irrigation conditions or the lack of conditions that meet their ecological requirements in this area. Also, the lack of data for some species (*Copris lunaris*, *Copris hispanus*, *Blaps halophile*) may be explained by their absence or unrecorded data during observations.

Overall, drip irrigation creates favorable microenvironments for some geophilous insects, maintaining optimal soil moisture. As a result, the diversity of

soil fauna and the abundance of some beneficial species increase. At the same time, some pest species can also develop.

In conclusion, the data in the table demonstrate that the composition of geophilous insects under drip irrigation conditions is significantly differentiated. This provides an important scientific basis for managing soil biological activity, preserving beneficial entomofauna, and developing integrated protection systems.

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